

Effect of Dexmedetomidine on Optic Nerve Sheath Diameter Changes in Laproscopic Hysterectomy; A Randomized Placebo Control TrialPankaj Kumar¹, Aditya Prakash², Mumtaz Hussain³, Akhileshwar⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Anesthesiology and Critical Care, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Science, Patna²Associate Professor, Medinirai Medical College Hospital, Palamu³Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Science, Patna⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Science, Patna

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Abstract:

Background: Dexmedetomidine (DEX) is a highly selective 2-agonist that provides sedation that is similar to that of natural sleep, anxiolysis, sympatholysis, and an anesthetic-sparing effect without causing clinically significant respiratory depression. These effects are all achieved without the use of barbiturates. The 2 adrenoceptors in the locus coeruleus of the central nervous system are responsible for the sedative effect that this substance has. It has been demonstrated that administering a single intraoperative dosage without following it up with an infusion can lessen the need for postoperative analgesics, facilitate a more seamless transition out of anesthesia, and extend the effects of regional anesthesia. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in the United States has given its current approval for the use of dexmedetomidine (brand name: Precedex) in the sedation of intubated adults via intravenous bolus and continuous infusion for up to 24 hours, as well as the sedation of non-intubated patients prior to or during surgical procedures and other procedures. DEX (Dexdor) was granted permission in 2011 by the European Union to be used for the indefinitely prolonged sedation of adult patients in intensive care units. Even though there is a substantial body of research supporting the use of DEX in paediatric anesthesia, the practice is still considered "off-label." Off-label uses of a medication refer to any applications of that medication that are not included on the product's prescription label. These include variations in dose, patient category, and the intended usage of the medication. Patients who are pregnant or children are more likely to be given drugs that are not approved for their condition by the manufacturer. Off-label use of a medication is permissible under certain circumstances, including when there is no other treatment option that would be more appropriate and when a doctor is certain that they are employing the medication in a manner that is in line with the most recent consensus in the medical community.

Keyword: Dexmedetomidine, Drug, Anaesthesia.

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Introduction

Gynecologists conduct hysterectomy for benign and malignant reasons (Aaarts et al., 2015). Hysterectomies are 90% for benign diseases. Leiomyomas, endometriosis/adenomyosis, and pelvic prolapse are the primary indications (ACOG, 2017). Hysterectomy is the ultimate therapy for the benign illnesses listed. Most women will have their uterus removed since it's the only way to permanently relieve discomfort. The size of the uterus, concomitant pathology, requirement for concurrent treatments, surgeon abilities and training, technological environment and support of the operating theatre, planned or emergent nature of the case, and patient desire might affect the route for benign disease hysterectomy. Abdominal, vaginal, laparoscopic, and robotic-assisted hysterectomy methods are used (RH). LH, performed by Harry Reich et al. in January 1988,

popularized laparoscopic hysterectomy. After then, eager pioneers claimed and scientifically reviewed this procedure. Evidence-based research suggest that LH is superior than AH in terms of postoperative morbidity, early return to normal activities, aesthetic outcomes, cost, and quality of care. Laparoscopic hysterectomy also adds additional problems. [1]

Several investigations have shown that artificial pneumoperitoneum increases intracranial pressure (ICP) during laparoscopy [2,3]. Increased intra-abdominal pressure, impaired cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) absorption and impeded drainage of the lumbar venous plexus, increased pressure in the vascular compartment of sacral spaces, Trendelenburg position, and cerebral vasodilation due to hypercarbia may increase ICP during

laparoscopy [3]. Although laparoscopy may create a serious cerebrovascular disadvantage, ICP is not measured since the most accurate approach is direct measurement of ICP using an intrusive monitoring device such as an extraventricular drain, which can induce severe bleeding or infection [4]. Transbulbar sonography ICP may now identify changed ICP non-invasively by measuring optic nerve sheath diameter (ONSD) [5]. ONSD assessment is a fast and non-invasive way to identify elevated ICP [6-7]. Despite its popularity, ultrasonography ONSD assessment was mostly employed in emergencies or critical care [8]. Ultrasonographic assessment of ONSD during robot-assisted laparoscopic radical prostatectomy with steep Trendelenburg orientation showed that ONSD rose 12.5% and that ICP could be anticipated [9]. No study has examined ONSD alterations following laparoscopic positioning modifications with short procedure time. If laparoscopic position affects ICP, ONSD should too. Thus, we examine ONSD change in laparoscopic surgery positional shift.

Clinical Trial Placebo: For decades, placebos have been thought of as inert controls and treatments in scientific experiments. Recent research shows that placebo effects are real psychobiological phenomena caused by the treatment environment and can be strong in lab and clinical settings. Even without a placebo, clinical trials show placebo benefits. [9] Placebo, meaning benign therapy to make a patient comfortable, has been used in medicine since the 18th century. [10] Post-World War II RCTs sparked interest in placebo effects. Several placebo-controlled studies have followed. Its utility in clinical studies is still contested. Clinical researchers' control experiments are placebos, usually sugar pills. A researcher compares the outcomes of an experimental therapy for an ailment to those of the placebo to prove a new treatment successful beyond the psychological effects of believing the medicine would cure. The placebo-controlled trial is considered the gold standard for assessing novel medicines.

Only after World War II did placebo-controlled clinical studies become popular. Randomized placebo-controlled (RCT) double-blind studies provided the greatest evidence for novel treatments. Placebo-controlled patients improved, sometimes drastically. Henry Beecher's proto meta-analysis popularized this result by claiming that 35% of patients reacted well to placebo therapy.

Laparoscopic Hysterectomy Ethics: Laparoscopic hysterectomy has a steeper learning curve and more problems than open abdominal hysterectomy. Indian postgraduate training is confined to conventional procedures and diagnostic laparoscopies. Gynecologists learn the method in brief, expensive training sessions that may only

entail mannequin training. Laparoscopic surgery is expensive.

Objective of the Study

1. Randomized placebo-controlled experiment of dexmedetomidine on optic nerve sheath diameter alterations in laparoscopic hysterectomy.

Research Methodology: This prospective study included 100 complete laparoscopic hysterectomy patients. A random number table split these patients into dexmedetomidine (n=50) and control (n=50) groups. The dexmedetomidine group received 0.5 µg/kg dexmedetomidine 10 min before anesthesia induction and 0.5 µg/(kg•h) until the completion of operation, whereas the control group received 0.9% sodium chloride solution. Both groups received mechanical ventilation following quick endotracheal intubation. The pneumoperitoneum pressure was 14 mmHg and the bispectral index was 40–60 intraoperatively. Ultrasonography was used to quantify ONSD in both groups at 5 min before induction of anesthesia in supine position (T1), 5 min after CO₂ pneumoperitoneum in Trendelenburg position (T2), 30 min, 60 min, and 5 min after the completion of the procedure (T5). Jugular venous oxygen saturation (SjvO₂), arterial content, arterial-to-internal jugular differential (Da-jvO₂), and cerebral oxygen extraction rate were studied between the two groups at different times (CERO₂). T1–T5 additionally captured HR and MAP. Each group also documented ASA grade, endotracheal extubation time, orientation recovery time, and postoperative adverse responses.

Anesthetics: Pre-op visits were made. Patients' general and medical histories were detailed. The inclusion and exclusion criteria were thoroughly assessed, and patients who did not fit them were eliminated.

Six-hour fasting and four-hour no-drinking were done before surgery. After patients entered the operating room, HR, MAP, oxygen saturation, and electrocardiogram were monitored. A 18-gauge needle opened right upper extremity peripheral venous access (BD Corporation, USA). BIS Complete (Aspect, USA) was used to assess anesthetic depth during surgery. The dexmedetomidine group received 0.5 µg/kg dexmedetomidine (20041731, Yangtze River Pharmaceutical Group, China) 10 min before anesthesia induction and 0.5 µg/(kg•h) during the procedure, whereas the control group received 0.9% sodium chloride solution (Pharmaceutical, India). Intravenous propofol, etomidate, sufentanil, and vicuronium bromide induced anesthesia. Patients received mask-fed oxygen for 3 minutes. After muscular relaxation, endotracheal intubation was used for assisted mechanical breathing. The respiratory parameters were 6-8 mL/kg tidal volume, 12-16 respiratory rate, 1:2 suction-to-exha-

lation ratio, 2.5 L/min oxygen flow, and 60% inhaled oxygen concentration. Intraoperatively, breathing parameters were modified to maintain end-tidal CO₂ partial pressure at 35-45 mmHg. Propofol-remifentanyl infusion pumps provided anesthesia. Intermittent bolus dosage of 1/3 to 1/2 the first dose of vicuronium bromide (00A06271, Yichang Ren-fu Pharmaceutical, China) was given. The BIS was 40–60 and the pneumoperitoneum pressure was 14 mmHg. Preoperative MAP was maintained $\pm$ 20%. MAP <60 mmHg was treated with an intravenous bolus of 6 mg ephedrine (200402, Shenyang No.1 Pharmaceutical, China) and accelerated infusion. Intravenous 0.5 mg atropine (201224, Broad Pharmaceutical, China) was given for HR <50 beats/min. After CO₂ pneumoperitoneum was achieved, the patient was head-down at 25–30 degrees. After closing the pneumoperitoneum, the patient was supine.

ONSD Measurements: Patients had portable color ultrasound eye scans (Sonosite, india). Sterile translucent dressing covered the patient's closed eyelids. The high-frequency linear array probe was equally coated with conductive gel to scan the cross-sectional and sagittal surfaces of one eyeball.

Ultrasonography-measured optic nerve sheath diameter: nutrition and organ health. Grade 2: Patients have surgical and moderate illnesses with good function compensation. Grade 3: Patients may manage daily tasks despite severe sickness and restricted physical exertion. Grade 4: Patients have serious illnesses, cease everyday activities, and often face death. Grade 5: Patients die within 24 hours regardless of surgery. Both groups recorded HR, MAP, endotracheal extubation, and orientation recovery time at T1-T5.

Postoperative complications: Both groups recorded postoperative dizziness, nausea, vomiting, and headache within 3 hours following surgery.

Statistical Analysis: In the pretest, dexmedetomidine group ONSD was 5.18 ± 0.13 mm at T3, while control group ONSD was 5.41 ± 0.14

The ultrasound probe was positioned horizontally or vertically on the patient's eyeball. To see the optic nerve sheath (ONS) without touching the eyeball, the probe angle and depth were slightly changed. An electronic caliper measured ONSD 3 mm behind the eyeball (see Figure 1). Cross-sectional and sagittal ONSD of both eyes were assessed. The average of the four ONSD measurements was 0.01 mm accurate [6].

Outcomes Measurements: Key outcomes: We measured ONSD in both groups at 5 min before induction of anesthesia in supine position (T1), 5 min after CO₂ pneumoperitoneum in Trendelenburg position (T2), 30 min, 60 min, and 5 min after the conclusion of the procedure (T5). COMT indications were recorded. Jugular bulbar and radial artery blood (3 ml) were taken from both groups at T1-T5 to measure jugular venous oxygen saturation (SjvO₂), arterial content, arterial-to-internal jugular differential (Da-jvO₂), and cerebral oxygen extraction rate (CERO₂). Secondary outcomes: Grades were ASA. Physical state and surgical risk determine ASA's five pre-anesthesia levels. Grade 1: Healthy, developed people

mm. With a two-tailed α of 0.05, a confidence coefficient of 95%, and a loss to follow-up rate of 20%, we projected 50 patients each group, hence this study comprised 100 patients.

Statisticians used SPSS 26.0. Mean $\pm$ standard deviation ($\bar{x} \pm sd$) was used for normal distribution data. Group t-tests and repeated measures analysis of variance were used to compare groups, while Pearson's chi-square test was used to evaluate count data. P-values <0.05 were significant.

Results

ONSD comparison: The control and dexmedetomidine groups had statistically significant changes in ONSD at T2-T5, but not at T1. Dexmedetomidine had a shorter ONSD at T2-T5 than control (P<0.05). Both groups had longer

ONSDs at T2-T5 than T1 (P<0.05). Table 2 and Figure 2.

Brain oxygen metabolism comparison: The control group had significantly different SjvO₂, Da-jvO₂, and CERO₂.

Table 1: General data comparison (x ± sd)

Case (n)	Dexmedetomidine group	Control group	t/χ ²	P
	(n=50)	(n=50)		
Types of diseases				
Uterine fibroids	20	21	0.045	0.832
Adenomyosis	17	16	0.049	0.824
Uterine fibroids with adenomyosis	9	8	0.089	0.764
Refractory dysfunctional uterine bleeding	4	5	0.155	0.694
ASA I/II	24/21	22/23	0.178	0.673
Age (years)	46.5±7.1	47.6±8.4	0.676	0.501
BMI (kg /m ²)	22.83±2.41	23.61±2.45	1.586	0.116
Pneumoperitoneum time (min)	112.46±10.63	109.09±11.41	1.413	0.161
Amount of bleeding (mL)	135.42±22.73	129.54±20.46	1.271	0.207
Amount of rehydration (L)	1.08±0.41	1.22±0.49	0.474	0.637

t: t-test; 2: Chi-squared test. BMI: BMI. Anesthesiologists, ASA.

Table 2: Optic nerve sheath diameter comparison (mm, x ± sd).

Group	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Dexmedetomidine group (n=50)	4.77±0.24	4.63±0.24 a,b	5.20±0.21a,b	4.71±0.22a,b	5.29±0.25a,b
Control group (n=50)	4.98±0.23	4.61±0.21 a	5.27±0.23a	4.84±0.26a	5.53±0.24a

Note: T1 aP<0.05, control group bP<0.05. T1: 5 min before induction of anesthesia in recumbent posture, T2: 5 min after CO₂ pneumoperitoneum in Trendelenburg position, T3: 30 min, T4: 60 min, T5: 5 min after the conclusion of the pneumoperitoneum.

Figure 2. ONSD time comparison. D group, dexmedetomidine; N group, control. T1 aP<0.05; control group bP<0.05. T1: 5 min before induction of anesthesia in reclined position, T2: 5 min after CO₂ pneumoperitoneum in Trendelenburg position, T3: 30 min, T4: 60 min, T5: 5 min after pneumoperitoneum closes in recumbent position.

and the dexmedetomidine group at T2-T5 (all P<0.05), and significant changes were identified within groups when comparing T2-T5 indicators to T1 indicators (P<0.05). HR-MAP comparison in Table 3.

HR did not change across groups at T1 (P>0.05). Dexmedetomidine reduced HR at T2-T5 (P<0.05). MAP was similar between groups at T1-T5 (P>0.05). Tables 4-5.

Comparison of endotracheal extubation time, orientation recovery time, and postoperative nausea, vomiting, headache, and dizziness within 3 hours following operation. Both groups had similar endotracheal extubation and orientation recovery times (P>0.05). Dexmedetomidine effectively reduced postoperative nausea, vomiting, headache, and dizziness within 3 hours after surgery (all P<0.05). Table 6.

Table 3: Laparoscopic surgery has less bleeding than open surgery,

Indicators	Group	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
SjvO ₂ (%)	Dexmedetomidine group (n=50)	57.72±9.05a,b	61.23±8.42	56.56±8.92a,b	58.57±8.93a,b	53.64±8.21a,b
	Control group (n=50)	53.40±8.81a	60.57±9.03	55.25±8.44a	56.21±8.56a	50.01±8.53a
Da-jvO ₂ (mmol/L)	Dexmedetomidine group (n=50)	53.43±4.98a,b	50.22±5.44	53.26±5.46a,b	52.62±5.23a,b	56.94±5.04a,b
	Control group (n=50)	60.49±5.45a	50.41±4.92	55.53±5.22a	56.84±4.99a	63.60±5.71a
CERO ₂ (%)	Dexmedetomidine group (n=50)	40.56±5.05a,b	35.22±4.87	38.20±4.86a,b	37.52±4.96a,b	41.25±4.87a,b
	Control group (n=50)	46±4.93a	34.71±4.66	42.04±5.03a	42.61±5.29a	48.67±5.41a

SjvO₂, jugular venous oxygen saturation; Da-jvO₂, arterial content and arterial-to-internal jugular differential; CERO₂, cerebral oxygen extraction rate. T1: 5 min before induction of anesthesia in reclined posture, T2: 5 min after CO₂ pneumoperitoneum in Trendelenburg position, T3: 30 min, T4: 60 min, T5: 5 min after the closing of pneumoperitoneum in recumbent position. T1, aP<0.05; control group, bP<0.05.

Table 4: Heart rate comparison (x ± sd).

Indicator	Group	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Heart rate (beat/min)	Dexmedetomidine group (n=50)	64.50±5.52a,b	55.57±4.68a,b	53.51±2.93a,b	62.58±8.54a,b	81.23±8.51
	Control group (n=50)	71.51±6.74a	69.53±6.82a	67.54±4.56a	73.56±6.81a	82.51±8.53

Note: T1 aP<0.05, control group bP<0.05. Finter-group=3.489, Pinter-group=0.003, Finteraction=0.937, Pinteraction=0.493.

T1: 5 min before induction of anesthesia in reclined posture, T2: 5 min after CO₂ pneumoperitoneum in Trendelenburg position, T3: 30 min, T4: 60 min, T5: 5 min after pneumoperitoneum closure in recumbent position.

Table 5: Mean arterial pressure comparison (x ± sd).

Indicator	Group	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Mean arterial pressure (mmHg)	Dexmedetomidine group (n=50)	89.93±7.45	87.65±8.09	88.43±6.46	87.41±6.48	90.71±10.92
	Control group (n=50)	88.41±8.56	89.69±7.58	87.61±5.93	88.75±7.65	89.44±9.58
t		1.415	1.839	1.696	1.03	1.63
P		0.161	0.093	0.093	0.406	0.107

t-test data. T1: 5 min before induction of anesthesia in reclined position, T2: 5 min after CO₂ pneumoperitoneum in Trendelenburg position, T3: 30 min, T4: 60 min, T5: 5 min after pneumoperitoneum closes in recumbent position.

Table 6: Extubation time, orientation recovery time, and total hospital stay Surgical nausea, vomiting, and headaches within 3 hours (n, %)

Group	Time of endotracheal extubation (min)	Recovery time for orientation (min)	Postoperative nausea and vomiting	postoperative headache	Dizziness
Dexmedetomidine group (n=50)	8.41±3.42	15.43±5.18	8 (17.78%)b	6 (13.43%)b	9 (20.00%)b
Control group (n=50)	7.96±4.14	14.12±6.41	22 (48.89%)	19 (42.42%)	25 (55.56%)
t/χ ²	0.437	0.921	9.801	9.46	12.1
P	0.737	0.459	0.002	0.002	0.001

t: t-test; 2: chi-square test. bP<0.05. postoperative headache and nausea. quicker recovery [10]. During surgery, patients should lie supine with their feet elevated above

their heads in the Trendelenburg position to ensure a favorable surgical field of vision and intra-abdominal pressure. Trendelenburg posture and pneumoperitoneum raise ICP [11, 12], causing

more postoperative headache and nausea than open cholecystectomy [13]. Long-term steep head-down posture and pneumoperitoneum cause serious neurological consequences [14, 15]. After pneumoperitoneal inflation, abdomen pressure might be transported to the chest cavity, increasing superior vena cava pressure and causing cerebral venous return disorders. In Trendelenburg position, gravity expands and congests the intracranial vein. Trendelenburg and pneumoperitoneal inflation raise ICP. CO₂ absorption produces hypercapnia and cerebral vasodilation. Non-neurological patients had elevated ICP of over 20 mmHg [16, 17]. MAP-ICP difference is cerebral perfusion pressure. Elevated ICP can lower cerebral perfusion pressure, which can be dangerous for older people with reduced cerebrovascular autoregulation or other cerebrovascular illness patients. Thus, intensive ICP-lowering therapies are essential for gynecological laparoscopic surgery patients. Obese adults had greater baseline ONSDs and broader ONSDs under pneumoperitoneum [16]. Heavyweight patients may have pleural fat, which reduces volume. CO₂ pneumoperitoneum raises intrathoracic pressure and worsens the ventilation/blood flow ratio. Another research found that younger patients had higher baseline ONSD values and quicker ONSD shifts in Trendelenburg position during laparoscopic surgery [17]. This may be because the elderly have low ONS flexibility and younger persons compensate faster for higher ICP than the old. ONS broadening causes ICP rise. ICP is cranial cavity wall pressure. Brain tissue, cerebro-spinal fluid, and blood arteries balance volume. ICP changes when volume balance breaks. Intracranial pressure usually rises. The cerebrospinal fluid in the optic nerve sheath and brain and spinal canal subarachnoid regions is continuous and communicates [18]. ICP raises brain subarachnoid pressure. Common pathways carry cerebrospinal fluid to the ONS sub-arachnoid region. The ONSD widens when cerebrospinal fluid squeezes the elastic ONS. Ultrasonographic ONSD measurement indirectly reflects ICP fluctuations [19].

Discussion

To reflect ICP, this experiment measured ONSD with an ultrasound 3 mm behind the eyeball. Normal ONSD was 5.1 (4.7-5.4) mm in 516 healthy Chinese individuals [20]. This study found no significant difference in ONSD at T1, although both groups had prolonged ONSD at T2-T5. Pneumoperitoneal compression and Trendelenburg position raise ICP. After a lengthy time in Trendelenburg position, ICP took time to recover, as the last ONSD measurement before patients left the operating room did not return to the baseline level. In Chinese individuals, ROC analysis indicated that ICP may surpass 20 mmHg when

ONSD exceeds 5.6 mm [21]. Only one patient in this trial had an ONSD >5.6 mm at two time points, and no surgical problems were detected.

Dexmedetomidine, a selective α_2 agonist that decreases opioid doses, is sedative, hypnotic, anxiolytic, and analgesic. Dexme-ICP detomidine's impact is debatable [23, 24]. Dexmedetomidine stimulates α_2A receptors to sedate, hypnotize, anti-vagal, and neuroprotect, and α_2B receptors to constrict cerebral blood vessels and lower cerebral blood flow [25]. All receptor subtypes inhibit norepinephrine release. These processes diminish brain metabolic rate, brain oxygen consumption, and ICP without ischemia [26]. In patients with traumatic brain injury, dexmedetomidine had no significant influence on cerebral blood flow ratio, brain metabolic rate, or cerebral blood volume, according to Farag's study [27]. Dexme-detomidine dose-dependently lowers brain metabolism in healthy people. Dexmedetomidine may increase brain oxygen demand without causing cerebral ischemia. Under normal blood volume, dexmedetomidine may reduce local cerebral blood flow and oxygen consumption [6]. Bleeding reduces cerebral blood flow more than oxygen consumption. Dexmedetomidine maintains the appropriate oxygen supply-to-use ratio following bleeding. α_2 agonists are better venous constrictors than arteriolar vasoconstrictors, and the majority of cerebral blood volume is in the venous compartments, thus they can lower intracranial pressure without significantly raising arteriolar cerebrovascular resistance. Dexmedetomidine may lower ICP during surgery.

In this investigation, ONSD at T2-T5 in the dexmedetomidine group were significantly shorter than those in the control group, indicating that it regulated ONSD in pneumoperitoneal and Trendelenburg posture. The central nervous system, sensitive to ischemia and hypoxia, balances brain oxygen supply and demand, reduces brain oxygen metabolism for cerebral protection of pneumoperitoneal patients in Trendelenburg position, and reduces post-operative neurological problems. Venous blood in the internal jugular vein globules mostly comes from the intracranial vein, hence S_{jo}O₂, D_a-j_vO₂, and CERO₂ might indirectly indicate brain oxygen metabolism under steady oxygen supply. S_{jo}O₂ and D_a-j_vO₂ increases suggest appropriate oxygen delivery to the cranial brain, whereas CERO₂ decreases imply improved cerebral perfusion. At T2-T5, the dexmedetomidine group had higher S_{jo}O₂, D_a-j_vO₂, and CERO₂ than the control group. Dexmedetomidine protects the brain. Its mechanism may include reducing brain tissue norepinephrine release, regulating the balance of preapoptosis and anti-apoptotic proteins, reducing glutamate release, and inhibiting calcium ion influx

[28]. Dexmedetomidine suppresses catecholamine production, reduces heart rate, and stabilizes intraoperative hemodynamics via the α_2 receptor [29].

The two groups had similar MAP at each time point in this investigation. Dexmedetomidine reduced HR at T2-T5. One patient received atropine and had no postoperative problems. Cerebrovascular arteries are affected by arterial blood CO₂ partial pressure. This investigation modified respiratory parameters to stabilize intraoperative end-expiratory carbon dioxide to eliminate this influence. Trendelenburg posture and high ICP produce nausea, vomiting, and headache following general anesthesia [30]. Yilmaz et al. reported that an increase in intraoperative ONSD is substantially linked with postoperative nausea and vomiting and headache within 3 h after surgery [31]. In this trial, dexmedetomidine reduced postoperative nausea and vomiting and headache within 3 hours following surgery. By lowering ICP, dexmedetomidine may indirectly reduce postoperative nausea, vomiting, and headache. Dexmedetomidine decreased postoperative adverse effects and did not affect endotracheal extubation or orientation recovery time in this research.

limitations in this study

This study has limitations. (1) Age did not categorize patients. Younger individuals can self-regulate the elevated ICP. (2) A multi-center big sample investigation is needed due to the short sample size. (3) Different angles and pressure on ONSD were not assessed to avoid affecting surgery. (4) ONSD indirectly represented ICP but not the genuine ICP.

Further research

In the future, we will be able to utilize transcranial Doppler for a more precise and intuitive monitoring of cerebral blood flow along with cerebral oxygen saturation in order to investigate the link between the Trendelenburg position and the increase in intracranial pressure (ICP). While this is going on, the incidence of problems like postoperative nausea and vomiting as well as postoperative headache can be discussed in order to shed light on the true clinical importance of this alteration. In addition, controlled investigations on the changes of ONSD that can be brought about by varying dosages of dexmedetomidine can be carried out.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the administration of dexmedetomidine during gynecological laparoscopic surgery in the Trendelenburg position effectively lowers the increased intracranial pressure (ICP) of patients, improves the oxygen metabolism in the brain, and lowers the incidence

of postoperative dizziness, nausea, and vomiting, as well as headaches.

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